

REVITALIZATION OF EDUCATION IN COLLEGES OF EDUCATION DURING COVID-19 PANDEMIC ERA IN SOUTHWEST NIGERIA: CONSEQUENCES AND PREVENTIVE MEASURES

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Abstract: Universally, education has been branded as a veritable tool of bringing about socio-cultural, political, and economic growth. COVID-19 pandemic, as a hindrance to education development, became a matter of concern to the world, Nigeria inclusive. It also affected the realization of Colleges of Education (CoE) national education objectives. This paper investigated the revitalization of education in Colleges of Education during the COVID-19 pandemic era in Southwest Nigeria: Consequences and preventive measures. The research design used was descriptive survey. The population for the study was all lecturers in CoEs in Southwest Nigeria. The study adopted a multi-stage sampling technique. All states in Southwest Nigeria were purposively selected through purposive sampling technique. These were Ekiti State, Lagos State, Ondo State, Oyo State, Ogun State, and Osun State. In each state, one state/Federal CoE was selected through random sampling technique. The selected CoEs were: Emmanuel Alayande CoE, Oyo, Oyo State; Tai Solarin CoE, Ijebu-Omu, Ogun State; Osun State CoE, Ilesa, Osun State; Federal CoE (Technical) Akoka, and Oyo State CoE, Lalante. Moreover, in each college, two schools were selected through random sampling technique. In each school, two departments were selected through random sampling technique. In each school, 10 lecturers were selected through random sampling technique. The structured questionnaire comprised two sections. Section A comprised items that sought to verify the respondents' demographic information. Section B comprised two parts: Part A sought information on the consequences of COVID-19 on CoEs education in Southwest Nigeria, while Part B comprised 10 items that sought to determine the solution to the upcoming effect of COVID-19 on CoEs education in Nigeria. A 4-Likert scale was adopted. The technique of data analysis was based on frequency distribution and simple percentages. Analysis revealed that all CoEs were shut down due to Federal and State government directives, ongoing examinations were canceled due to the COVID-19 outbreak. Also, the implementation of syllabuses became

unrealistic in CoEs, and syllabuses were unattained because students could not attend schools. Equally, preventive approaches were acknowledged, such as curfew declarations nationwide to prevent the spread and mass media education to sensitize people. Modifications in the educational system for future occurrences were also emphasized, making online learning more valued. Thus, for CoEs in Nigeria to effectively compete globally in the quality of teaching, research, international outlook, and innovation, there is a need for strategies for controlling futuristic occurrences: sustainable internet lecturing, good communication networking, and standard medical facilities factors which are crucial to education development should be made available.

Keywords: Covid-19 pandemic era, Sustainable internet lecturing, Good medical facilities, Good communication networking, Education development

Introduction

The deadly pandemic - Coronavirus disease 2019 (COVID-19) was authoritatively announced by the Director General of the World Health Organization (WHO) on January 30, 2020 (Public Health Emergency of International Concern, PHEIC, 2020). Likewise, on February 27, 2020, the Federal Ministry of Health (FMH, 2020) announced the authentication of the first case of Coronavirus disease in Lagos State, Nigeria. In the same communication, the FMH announced that the Multi-sectorial Coronavirus Preparedness Group, led by the Nigeria Center for Disease Control (NCDC, 2020), had immediately activated its National Emergency Operations Center. Since then, in less than 2 months, Nigeria reached more than 50 cases across the country. On March 19, 2020, a circular from the Federal Ministry of Education (FME, 2020) granted approval for the closure of all schools for a period of one (1) month, commencing from Monday, March 23, 2020, to prevent the spread of the virus.

This outbreak of COVID-19 is a global health emergency. On February 27, Nigeria confirmed its first case in Lagos State, an Italian citizen who worked in Nigeria and had returned on February 25 from Milan, Italy, through the Murtala Muhammed International Airport. He fell ill on February 26 and was transferred to Lagos State Biosecurity Facilities for isolation and testing. Presently, Nigeria has 199 COVID-19 cases, two deaths, and twenty recovered. In order to contain the spread of the virus in Nigeria, the Federal Ministry of Education has directed all educational institutions in Nigeria to shut down and allow students to go home as reported COVID-19 cases increased to 13. The FME (2019) reported on March 19 that the directive was part of the country's overall strategy to contain the spread of the virus. Nigeria joins the growing list of countries in Africa which have closed schools and universities. Before the official announcement by the permanent secretary, most universities had already sent their students home (Wikipedia, 2020; Olayiwola, Oladimeji, Fadare, Egbedokun, and Ajobo, 2022).

According to the WHO (2020), coronaviruses are a family of viruses that cause illnesses ranging from the common cold to more severe diseases such as severe acute respiratory syndrome (SARS) and the Middle East respiratory syndrome (MERS). These viruses were originally transmitted from animals to people. SARS, for instance, was transmitted from civet cats to humans, while MERS moved to humans from a type of camel. Several known coronaviruses are circulating in animals that have not yet infected humans. The name coronavirus comes from the Latin word "corona," meaning crown or halo. Under an electron microscope, it looks like it is surrounded by a solar corona. The novel coronavirus, identified by Chinese authorities on January 7, and since named SARS-

CoV-2, is a new strain that had not been previously identified in humans. Little is known about it, although human-to-human transmission has been confirmed (Olayiwola, Oladimeji, Fadare, Egbedokun and Ajobo, 2022).

The COVID-19 pandemic has not stopped at national borders. It has affected people regardless of nationality, level of education, income, or gender. But the same has not been true for its consequences, which have hit the most vulnerable hardest. Education is no exception. This crisis has exposed the many inadequacies and inequities in our education systems from access to broadband and computers needed for online education, and the supportive environments needed to focus on learning, up to the misalignment between resources and needs (Andreas, 2020). The lockdowns in response to COVID-19 have interrupted conventional schooling with nationwide school closures. While the educational community has made concerted efforts to maintain learning continuity during this period, children and students have had to rely more on their own resources to continue learning remotely through the internet, television, or radio. Lecturers also had to adapt to new pedagogical concepts and modes of delivery for teaching, for which they may not have been trained.

In particular, learners in the most marginalized groups, who don't have access to digital learning resources or lack the resilience and engagement to learn on their own, are at risk of falling behind. With this new order, the state of the implementation of the 2030 education agenda, which aimed to "ensure inclusive and equitable quality education and promote lifelong learning opportunities for all," may face delay due to the short- or long-term effect of the COVID-19 pandemic and consequently may affect the right to education of children with disabilities (Olayiwola, 2022). As a result, this paper aims to examine the impact of the revitalization of education in Colleges of Education during the COVID-19 pandemic era in Southwest Nigeria: Consequences and preventive measures. According to WHO (2020), which comprises the record of about 25 countries globally renowned for a substantial number of 28,276 confirmed cases and 565 death tolls. In the ensuing months, it prevails in every nook and cranny of the world, with confirmed cases of 8,060,496 contagious cases and 437,054 deaths (Education in Emergency Working Group (EiEWG), 2020).

However, when the virus wave became apparent and difficult to control, world leaders imposed partial or complete closure of public gatherings. As such, it raised some speculations by the leaders of the nation on the stance of whether partial lockdown or complete lockdown would serve on the hotspots of the pandemic. Besides, the lockdown decision may negatively impact the economy and particularly the social well-being of the society. So, how to balance this complicated social, economic, and health puzzle became an issue of international concern (Shaheen et al., 2020). The world has been affected by the novel COVID-19 pandemic.

In the case of Nigeria, it could neither remain immune to the global catastrophe. The first confirmed COVID-19 case was publicized on February 27, 2020. To ensure the continuity of education despite the lockdown, higher education institutions have sought to use technology and offer online classes and learning experiences as a substitute for in-class time. However, many institutions struggled and lacked the experience and time they needed to conceive new ways to deliver instruction and assignments. Examinations were also affected, causing disruption to students' learning trajectories and progression. Although many higher education institutions offered online courses before the pandemic, few students considered it as the sole alternative to physical in-person learning (UNESCO, 2020).

Countries used a variety of resources to support students' learning while they were unable to come to school, including instructional packages (textbooks, worksheets, and printouts), radio education, educational television, and online instructional resources. Countries usually used several tools in order to reach the largest

proportion of students possible. In developed countries, online platforms were the most popular tool used during school closures (90% of countries used this approach), while in low- and lower-middle-income countries, online learning was used much less frequently 45% (UNESCO, 2020).

Table1: Methods Adopted During Covid-19 In Selected Countries.

Country	Teaching Method/Education Strategies Adopted During Covid-19 Era
Estonia	Collaborated with private services to provide a wealth of educational content free to students during school closure.
France	Already- existing distance learning programme “Maclasseàlamaison” (My classes at home) available for students in primary and secondary schools
Greece	Lecturers conducted virtual real-time classes in conjunction with other online learning tools
OECD countries	Learning arrangement were by government television broadcasts providing educational learning.
Greece, Korea & Portugal	Some had difficulty using online learning self-directed learning.TV broadcasts were used to reach those who do not have adequate resources for online instruction.
Mexico	Telephone line “Your Teacher Online” has been activated to offer Mentoring to students
Spain	TV covered one of five subjects(Spanish, Mathematics, Social science, Natural sciences And Arts and/or Physical education)per day during a one-hour slot
Luxembourg	Government setup an e-support system for students and parents to support Home schooling
Finland, Japan & Netherlands	Individual schools had more autonomy in organizing alternative education arrangements
Africa countries Burkina Faso	Total country-wide closure of educational institutions
South Africa	Some universities' decision to open their schools for online learning

Table 1: Teaching method/educational strategies adopted during Covid-19 by selected countries

Sources: UNESCO (2020); Schleicher and Reimers, (2020); Ministry of Education and Vocational Training, (2020); OECD, 2020.

Theoretical Framework for the Study

Social Constructivism explains teaching and learning as social phenomena between lecturers and learners (Taguma, Feron, & Lim, 2018). In Yunusa, Sanusi, Dada, Oyelere, Agbo, Obaido, and Aruleba (2021), it is a clear departure from the idea that lecturers are custodians of knowledge; instead, the theory considers lecturers as facilitators in the learning process. Advocates of this theory believe that learning is about finding solutions to problems and that the social construction of solutions is the essence of the learning process (Picciano, 2017). In other words, problem-solving through collaboration is the primary objective of social constructivism. Many social media solutions developed for collaborations are leveraged in this COVID-19 pandemic and social distancing era. In the view of social constructivists, lecturers could develop social relationships with their students to support their remote learning during school closure. Connectivism is often referred to as the learning theory for the digital era, as it describes how people learn in today’s “technology-driven” society (Shrivastava, 2018). According to Siemen (2005), knowledge does not only reside in the mind of a person but in a distributed manner across a

network. This study regards the connectivist viewpoint as the most relevant learning paradigm in this current situation, where students are confined to learning at home due to the COVID-19 pandemic.

Firstly, connectivism theory captures the importance of online collaborative learning and sharing in this age. Secondly, social constructivism primarily focuses on problem-solving through collaboration. That is, the teacher is seen as a modifier of education. Also, connectivism is the only theory that recognizes the presence of the internet and best explains how people learn in the era of ever-increasing and rapidly changing information due to technology advancement and the ubiquitous access to the Internet. Thirdly, according to Kropf (2013), connectivism fosters the “design of learning materials, resources, or situations to help learners achieve their learning outcomes and maximize their learning potential.”

Literature Review

Despite the alternative learning measures adopted by some of these countries, many students are excluded from the educational process. According to UNESCO (2020) as cited in Huang et al., 2020, as of April 2020, over 1.5 billion learners have been excluded from the normal learning process across the globe due to school closure measures. From the African perspective, statistics from UNESCO on the impact of COVID-19 on education, as of the time this study was conducted, show that all countries in Africa except Burkina Faso had a country-wide closure of educational institutions (UNESCO, 2020). This indicates that the impact is perceived to be more in those regions that had country-wide closures if alternative means of teaching and learning were not provided.

For instance, in the case of South Africa, the study by Ojo & Onwuegbuzie (2020) revealed that some universities' decision to open their schools for online learning in April 2020 created mixed reactions among their students. Most of the students complained about several inconveniences they encountered by studying from home. The study revealed issues such as noise and disturbances from the home environment, limited Internet connection, and lack of consistent electricity, which affects their academic performance. In addition, the government of South Africa had directed that each university should make a mitigation plan, that is, online study delivery as an alternative method for teaching and learning to curb the spread of the disease (Chothia, 2020).

While it seems that the devastation caused by COVID-19 on education has pushed most nations to seek an alternative for teaching and learning, South African scholars have expressed concern over the level of training and experience of educators in the pedagogy for effective delivery of online learning (Hedding et al., 2020). As part of the effort to create more opportunities to learn during the lockdown in South Africa, a study by Mhlanga & Mloi (2020) reported the launching of “STEM Lockdown Digital School.” This involved an initiative where more than 34 public and private school lecturers were organized to teach through a live stream on “Africa Teen Geek’s” social media pages such as Facebook, Twitter, and Ms. Zora.

A similar experience was reported in the northern part of Africa. For example, a report from Egypt shows that most private universities in the country switched to online teaching through Moodle, Microsoft class Notes, Microsoft Teams, email, and Zoom (UN, 2020). In Nigeria, over 39 million learners, including pre-primary and tertiary students, were asked to stay at home during the pandemic situation (UNESCO, 2020). Consequently, students face barriers from accessing learning materials, receiving mentorship, counseling from lecturers, and other supports that are easily made available in a face-to-face learning environment. Besides, lecturers are not left out of the impact of school closure due to the COVID-19 pandemic. Reports from some parts of the world suggest that lecturers will experience temporary or permanent layoffs during and post-COVID-19.

The research by Shrivastava (2018) demonstrated how connectivism fosters lifelong learning in students by conducting an exercise between student groups in two different institutions based in two different countries.

Similarly, research found that the use of a web-based instructional model based on connectivism raised the level of students' problem-solving skills in ICT for daily life (Sitti, Sopeerak, & Sompong, 2013). Consequently, this study was grounded on the premise of social constructivism (Vygotsky & Cole, 2018) and the connectivism learning theory (Siemens, 2005), given that the study sought to understand how the social distancing measures, school closures, and emergency remote learning, adopted to navigate the challenges posed by the COVID-19 pandemic, impacted the connection with students and contemporaries.

COVID-19 and Tertiary Education

The negative impact of the COVID-19 pandemic across global education, including Nigeria, cannot be overlooked. The International Labour Organisation (ILO) (2020) has estimated that full or partial lockdown measures now affect almost 2.7 billion workers, representing around 81% of the world's workforce, while the IMF projects a significant contraction of global output in 2020. COVID-19 is lurching the world economy towards a global recession, which will be strikingly different from past recessions. In contrast, developing countries, particularly in sub-Saharan Africa, constrained by low financial muscle, poor internet infrastructure, competing budgetary needs, and personnel skill gaps are struggling to cope with the disruptions caused by the pandemic. Despite the handful of efforts made by some state governments in Nigeria to adopt the alternative teaching model or e-Learning programs (such as television and radio school broadcasts), more than 75% of the federation states had their schools under lockdown.

However, there is an apparent lack of evidence-based data on the success of the e-Learning solutions and the extent of the organizational, institutional, and digital skill readiness in delivering optimal teaching and learning outcomes using the flexible learning or remote learning medium during health emergencies. Understanding these phenomena is essential because it helps guide curriculum and instruction design that optimizes citizens' learning opportunities and provides insights into how resource-constrained communities could deal with educational challenges during health emergencies and academic disruptions (UNESCO, 2022; Adeoye, Adanikin & Adanikin, 2020). Beyond the disparate forms in which the Coronavirus has impacted on the wider spectrum of entities in education, the pandemic offers a window of opportunities for new experiences, reimagining the educational process, and extending the frontiers of knowledge through empirical research and experimentation of different learning pedagogies and the use of technology. Also, it unravels the competences, availability, and infrastructural adequacy for remote learning within the context of Nigeria; and identifies sustainable practices that will inform curriculum planning, design, and implementation for an effective response to similar crises and during the period post-pandemic.

The COVID-19 pandemic has also had a severe impact on higher education as schools closed their premises and countries shut their borders in response to lockdown measures. When higher education institutions were quick to replace face-to-face lectures with online learning in countries such as the US, Canada, and European countries, Nigerian institutions were shut down without efforts to provide alternatives. These closures affected institution academic learning and examinations as well as the safety of students across campuses in the country. Not only did the closure of schools affect close to 46 million students throughout the country, the most vulnerable groups of children targeted by the education partners were affected most. About 400,000 IDP children attending some forms of learning in the camps and host communities were affected by the stoppage of learning activities. Planned activities for the first and second quarter of 2020 will not be completed as planned before the pandemic started (FMH, 2020).

In light of the far-reaching consequences of the COVID-19 pandemic on education systems around the world, with 89% of the world's student population affected by COVID-19 school closures as of 1 April 2020, governments and partner organizations have ramped up efforts to facilitate the continuity of learning (Akinyemi, Fakorede, Anjorin, Abegunrin, Adunmo & Ajoseh, 2020). It is important to acknowledge that the current crisis will have long-lasting consequences for education systems in terms of access, quality, equity, and management, which are likely to persist beyond the pandemic. According to Viner et al., (2020), as of the 18th of March 2020, 107 countries had closed their schools in response to the spiraling coronavirus (COVID-19) virus. Nonetheless, some countries activated the UN's charter on alternative teaching models during the crisis period. In addition, the United Nations Educational, Scientific, and Cultural Organization (UNESCO) reported that over 800 million children stayed at home for nearly a year, following the worldwide closure of schools.

Problem of the Study

The news of Coronavirus, also known as COVID-19 was disseminated on social media from Wuhan, Republic of China in the late 2019. The pandemic affected teaching and learning and along interruption in the educational system globally. This pandemic challenged Nigeria education system at all levels particularly tertiary institutions. Nigeria is not technological equipped for virtual teaching and learning like other developed nations, just few private universities in the country can engage in virtual learning. This is not as effective as classroom teaching which enhances proper assimilation of subject matter.

Previous studies focused on covid-19 pandemic as relates to teaching and learning, delivering quality education, educational resources, environment, access learning, and virtual learning and soon with little or no attention on how Colleges of Education was affected during the Covid-19 pandemic. Thus, this steered sougning the education development in Colleges of Education during Covid-19 pandemic era in Southwest Nigeria and identified consequences and preventive measures for future occurrence.

Purpose of the Study

The purpose of the study was to revitalization of education in Colleges of Education during Covid-19 pandemic era in Southwest Nigeria: Consequences and preventive measures. Specifically,

1. To examine the consequences of Corona Virus (COVID-19) Pandemic on education in Colleges of Education during Covid-19 pandemic era in Southwest, Nigeria.
2. Proffer way forward to consequences of Corona Virus (COVID-19) Pandemic on education in Colleges of Education during Covid-19 pandemic era in Southwest, Nigeria.

Research Questions

The following research questions were raised and answered:

1. What are the consequences of the Coronavirus (COVID-19) pandemic on education activities in Colleges of Education during the COVID-19 pandemic era in Southwest, Nigeria?
2. Are there preventive methods to curb the consequences of the Coronavirus (COVID-19) pandemic in Colleges of Education in the nearest future in Southwest, Nigeria?

Methodology

The design for the study was a descriptive survey type. The population of the study consisted of all lecturers in Colleges of Education in Southwest, Nigeria. A Multi-stage Sampling Technique was adopted.

Stage 1: All states in Southwest, Nigeria, were purposively selected through a purposive sampling technique. These states were Ekiti State, Lagos State, Ondo State, Oyo State, Ogun State, and Osun State.

Stage 2: In each state, one state or Federal Government College of Education was selected through random sampling technique. The selected Colleges of Education were:

1. Emmanuel Alayande College of Education, Oyo, Oyo State,
2. Tai Solarin College of Education, Ijebu-Omu, Ogun State,
3. Osun State College of Education, Ilesa, Osun State,
4. Federal College of Education (Technical), Akoka, and
5. Oyo State College of Education, Lalante.

Stage 3: In each college, two schools were selected through random sampling technique, considering them as part of the system. A total of 10 schools were selected.

Stage 4: In each school, two departments were selected through random sampling technique. A total of 20 departments were selected.

Stage 5: In each school, 10 lecturers were selected through random sampling technique. A total of 200 lecturers were used for the study.

Instrumentation

An instrument labelled “Colleges of Education and Covid-19 Pandemic Era Questionnaire” (CECPQ) was used to collect data. The questionnaire was divided into three sections:

Section A contained respondents' personal data, such as gender, age, educational qualifications, experience, etc.

Sections B consisted of two parts with 10 items each. The format adopted for Section B was a Likert scale format in which respondents were required to respond.

Experts in the field of Educational Management and Teacher Education validated the instrument. Corrections were made before the administration of the questionnaire. The test and retest method was used, and a reliability coefficient of 0.72 was obtained. Simple percentage analysis was used to analyze the two research questions.

Results

What are the consequences of the Coronavirus (COVID-19) pandemic on education in Colleges of Education during the COVID-19 pandemic era in Southwest, Nigeria?

Table1: Consequences of Corona Virus (COVID19) on the Education in CoE

S/N	Items	SA (%)	A (%)	D (%)	SD (%)
1.	All Colleges of Education were shut due to Federal and state government directives	170(85.00)	20(10.00)	10 (5.00)	0 (0.00)
2.	Some CoEs on-going examinations were cancelled and later re-organized	150(75.00)	0(0.00)	30 (15.00)	20 (10.00)
3.	Implementation of syllabuses become unrealistic In Colleges of Education	190 (95.00)	10. (5.00)	0 (0.00)	0 (0.00)
4.	Teaching and learning process was halted in Colleges of Education	130 (65.00)	70(35.00)	0 (0.00)	0 (0.00)
5.	Lecturers salaries and supplementary benefits were not paid (at times not regular)	100 (50.00)	90(45.00)	0 (0.00)	10 (5.00)
6	Prolong time for learners to complete their Academic programme(s)	140(70.00)	60(30.00)	0 (0.00)	0 (0.00)
7	Admission of new students were delayed. Thus, academic calendars/academic exercise programme were canceled	100 (50.00)	75 (37.5)	0 (0.00)	25 (12.50)
8	Cancellation and re-scheduling of educational Programmes in Colleges of Education	120 (60.00)	80 (40.00)	0 (0.00)	0 (0.00)
9	No enrolment of students in Colleges of Education	150(75.00)	50(25.00)	0(0.00)	0(0.00)
10	No promotion and graduation ceremonies in Colleges of Education	180 (90.00)	20 (10.00)	0 (0.00)	0 (0.00)

Table 1 shows the consequences of Corona Virus (COVID - 19) Pandemic on education in Colleges of Education during Covid-19 pandemic era in Southwest, Nigeria. It was found that 170 (85.00%) strongly agreed, 20(10.00%) agreed while 10 (5.00%) disagreed that all Colleges of Education were shut due to Federal and state government directives. All the respondents, 150(100.00%) respondents strongly agreed that some CoEs on going examinations were cancelled and later re-organized due to unannounced event of Covid-19. On the motion that implementation of syllabuses become unrealistic in CoEs as a results the pandemic, 190 (95.00%) respondents strongly agreed while 10 (5.00%) agreed. More so, the study revealed that 100 (50.00%) respondents strongly agreed while 90 (45.00%) respondents agreed. In addition, 100 (50.00%) respondents strongly agreed, 75 (37.50%) respondents agreed while 25(12.50%) strongly disagreed. Also, 150 (75.00%) respondents strongly agreed while 50(25.00%)

respondents agreed on the view. Apart from that, it was discovered that 180(90.00) and 20 (10.00%) agreed that there was no promotion and graduation of graduates from the CoEs.

Research Question 2: Are the preventive methods to curb consequences of Corona Virus (COVID-19) Pandemic in Colleges of Education in the nearest future in Southwest, Nigeria?

Table 2: Preventive Methods to Consequences of Corona Virus (COVID-19) Pandemic on CoE

S/N	Items	SA (%)	A (%)	D (%)	SD (%)
1.	Declaration of curfew nationwide to prevent spreading of such pandemic	140.0(70.00)	50.0(25.00)	10.0 (5.00)	0.0 (0.00)
2.	Public enlightens on Covid-19 pandemic should projected to make the public aware	175.0(75.00)	0.0(0.00)	25.0 (12.50)	0.0 (0.00)
3.	Provision of palliatives to those that are less Privileged	160.0 (80.00)	40.0 (20.00)	0.0 (0.00)	0.0 (0.00)
4.	Closing of interstate and national borders Particularly air transport	100.0 (50.0)	70.00(35.0)	30.0 (15.0)	0.0 (0.00)
5.	Re-adjustment/of educational system for the school system to operate.	100.0 (50.00)	90.0(45.00)	0.0 (0.00)	10.0 (5.00)
6	Religious/Social gathering must be prohibited.	140.0(70.00)	60.0(30.00)	0.0 (0.00)	0.0 (0.00)
7	Strict the interregional and-state transportation.	75.00 (35.7)	100.0 (50.0)	0.0 (0.00)	25.0 (12.50)
8	Health directives should be honored to save guard the blow out of such pandemic	120.0 (60.00)	80.0 (40.00)	0.0 (0.00)	0.0 (0.00)
9	There should be curfew to prevent economic activities	190.0(95.00)	10.0 (5.00)	0.0 (0.00)	0.00 (0.00)
10	Online (e learning) teaching and learning should be adopted	130.0 65.00)	50.00 (25.00)	20.00 (10.00)	0.00 (0.00)

Table 2 displays preventive methods to curb consequences of Corona Virus (COVID-19) Pandemic in Colleges of Education in the nearest future in Southwest, Nigeria. Findings showed that 140 (70.00%) respondents strongly agreed, and 50 (25.00%) respondents agreed that the declaration of curfew nationwide by the government should prevent the spread of such pandemic, respectively, while 20 (5.00%) respondents disagreed. Additionally, 175 (75.00%) respondents strongly agreed, while 50 (12.50%) respondents agreed that mass media education should be on air to sensitize people on environmental issues. Furthermore, 160 (80.00%) respondents agreed that provision of palliatives to those who are less privileged should be prioritized, while 40 (20.00%) respondents disagreed.

On the statement regarding modifications in the educational system for future pandemics, 100 (50.00%) respondents strongly supported it, while 90 (45.00%) respondents agreed, and 5 (5.00%) respondents strongly disagreed. Moreover, 120 (60.00%) respondents strongly maintained that there is a need to obey health directives to safeguard against the spread of such pandemics, while 80 (40.00%) respondents agreed. On the statement that online learning will be more valued than classroom learning, 130 (65.00%) respondents strongly supported the motion, while 50 (25.00%) agreed, and 20 (10.00%) respondents disagreed.

Discussion of Findings

Table 1 addresses the consequences of the COVID-19 pandemic in Colleges of Education in Southwest, Nigeria. It was found that all Colleges of Education were shut due to Federal and State government directives. As a result, some ongoing CoEs examinations were cancelled and later re-organized due to the unannounced onset of Covid-

19. As a result of this, the implementation of syllabuses became unrealistic in many of CoEs. Moreover, it was discovered that there was no promotion and graduation of graduates from the CoEs. It might take a longer time to complete syllabuses because lecturers and students could not meet for classroom interactions. Also, during Covid-19, teaching and learning could not take place in the Colleges of Education, as lecturers stayed at home, thus, they could not participate in academic exercises. Students always use more extra time for academic programmes, as there have been changes that involve cancellation and re-scheduling of educational programmes, and there were no promotion and graduation ceremonies in the schools.

This is in line with the opinion of the Federal Ministry of Health (FMH, 2020) that COVID-19 pandemic was the reason for the closure of schools and this affected close to 46 million students throughout the country. The most vulnerable groups of children targeted by the education partners are likely to be impacted the most. About 400,000 IDP children attending some forms of learning in camps and host communities were affected by the stoppage of learning activities. In light of the far-reaching consequences of the COVID-19 pandemic on education systems around the world, with 89% of the world's student population affected by COVID-19 school closures as of 1 April 2020, governments and partner organizations have ramped up efforts to facilitate the continuity of learning. More so, Table 2 presents the preventive approaches to the consequences of the Corona Virus (COVID-19) pandemic in Colleges of Education in Southwest, Nigeria, were highlighted. The respondents strongly pointed out that to prevent the spread of such a pandemic, the government should declare curfew nationwide. Mass media education should be on air to sensitize people on environmental issues. Also, modifications in the educational system for future pandemics indicate that online learning will be more valued than classroom learning, meaning that virtual learning can be used alternatively.

In addition, the declaration of a national curfew nationwide to prevent the spread of such pandemics, Covid-19 pandemic awareness should be on air regularly, and social/religious gatherings must be prohibited. There is a need to obey health directives to safeguard against the spread of such a pandemic.

This study is in line with the observation of OECD (2020), that despite these significant challenges, humanitarian and development organizations and governments are implementing a range of interventions. Although students with access to digital devices and internet may not be the majority in most countries, supporting governments in establishing effective forms of online education will free up institutional capacities and resources in order to redirect their focus on delivering alternative learning methods for those students who do not have similar opportunities.

Conclusion

The pandemic has pushed the world into the deepest global recession in living memory, which will have lasting effects on education. The Federal and State governments must protect education financing through strengthening domestic revenue mobilization, preserving the share of expenditure for education as a top priority, and addressing inefficiencies in education spending. Strengthening the resilience of education systems enables countries to respond to the immediate challenges of safely reopening schools and positions them to better cope with future

crises. In this regard, governments could consider equity and inclusion, reinforce capacities at all levels, particularly secondary education nationwide.

Recommendations

Based on the findings, recommendations were made that:

- For Colleges of Education in Nigeria to effectively compete globally in the quality of teaching, research, international outlook, and innovation, there is an urgent need for technological innovative strategies for addressing futuristic occurrences through sustainable internet lecturing (online learning).
- Colleges of Education management should adopt alternative teaching models or mass learning programs (such as television and radio school broadcasts) as being practice in Distance Learning Programme.
- Information and Communication Technology (ICT) facilities should be provided by the state and federal governments in COEs to enhance students and lectures interest and on line usage.
- There is need for regular public enlightenment on health directives to safeguard against the widespread of such pandemics in the nearest future.
- The Ministry of Education should be at alert in the nearest future toward re-adjustment of the educational system to suit world standards for the CoEs to operate during unexpected pandemics.

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